

Open Science Meetings

Call for proposals

Open Science NL

2025

Content

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Background	1
1.2	Available budget	2
1.3	Submission deadline(s)	2
2	Aim	3
2.1	Aim of the programme	3
3	Conditions for applicants	4
3.1	Who can apply	4
3.2	What can be applied for	5
3.3	Preparing an application	7
3.4	Conditions for submission	8
3.5	Conditions on granting	9
4	Assessment procedure	11
4.1	The San Francisco Declaration (DORA)	11
4.2	Procedure	11
4.3	Criteria	13
5	Obligations for grant recipients	14
5.1	Additional terms and conditions	14
6	Contact and other information	15
6.1	Contact	15
6.2	Other information	15
7	Annexes	16
7.1	Open Science	16

1 Introduction

In this Call for proposals information is provided about the application procedure for the “Open Science Meetings” funding round. This Call for proposals falls under the responsibility of Open Science NL, part of the Dutch Research Council (NWO). Open Science NL mission is to establish open Science as the norm in the Netherlands. One way to accomplish this is providing funding for projects that enable this transition. Another way is to monitor progress, facilitate knowledge exchange and coordinating the national covenant consultation, in order to shape the national open science agenda.

In this Call for proposals you will find information about the aim of this programme (Chapter 2), the conditions for the grant application (Chapter 3) and how your proposal will be assessed (Chapter 4). This is the information you need to submit a grant application. Chapter 5 states the obligations for grant recipients in the event you are awarded funding. Chapter 6 contains the contact details and Chapter 7 the annexes.

1.1 Background

The Dutch government has made available substantial funding to support the transition to open science in the Netherlands. The aim of the investment is to make open science the norm.

This Call falls within the first work programme of Open Science NL, which covers the years 2024-2025.

The instruments within this work programme cover the following priority areas:

1. Capacity building,
2. Infrastructure for Open Science,
3. Robust research processes,
4. Evidence base for Open Science,
5. Empowering communities.

This work programme addresses a comprehensive set of needs and range of areas relating to open science and provides a strong basis from which the uptake of open science practices can continue to grow and flourish in the Netherlands.

The “Open Science Meetings” Call falls under the priority area “Empowering communities”. Communities are groups of people who share particular attitudes and common interests. In the case of this Work Programme, this means an interest in open science. They can be formed by and for researchers, research support staff, policy officers and practitioners (also outside of knowledge institutions). Community members come together, exchange ideas, and collaborate in searching for solutions to challenges and problems they have in common. Communities play a key role in the transition to open science as catalysts for collaboration, inspiration, training and (bottom-up) initiatives.

Communities foster a sense of peer support, ownership and engagement that encourages active participation in open science initiatives. By ensuring that diverse perspectives and voices are heard, collaboration within communities can lead to innovative approaches and to more relevant and impactful solutions that are tailored to the needs and priorities of community members. Importantly, empowered communities become advocates, raising awareness about the benefits of open science practices and promoting its values and principles. Empowering and supporting community efforts is therefore a priority.

This Call for Proposals is aimed at supporting communities in organising (international) meetings.

1.1.1 Changes since the previous Call for proposals

The following changes have been made compared to the previous Call for proposals:

- A limited set of societal parties may act as co-applicant, if they are able to provide a de minimis statement;
- Meetings to accommodate training regarding open science topics are allowed;
- The provided reimbursement is increased to € 100 per participant *per day*.
- An additional reimbursement of maximum € 2,000 is now allowed for travel and accommodation of foreign speakers. You can apply for a maximum of five (5) foreign speakers in total.
- Printing costs for promotional materials are now eligible for funding.

1.2 Available budget

The available budget for this Call for proposals is € 300,000.

1.3 Submission deadline(s)

The final deadline for submitting a proposal is **11 December 2025, before 14:00:00 hours CET**.

An application for a meeting must be submitted to Open Science NL a minimum of six weeks and a maximum of twelve months before the meeting takes place. Open Science NL will handle applications that meet the formal requirements in order of receipt. If the limit of the available budget has been reached, the funding instrument will be closed.

2 Aim

This chapter describes the aim of the programme and the societal impact.

2.1 Aim of the programme

Many communities related to open science are currently forming, consolidating or expanding, across all relevant research performing organisations and supporting institutions. Bottom-up support will benefit these communities and the connections between them by allowing open science practices to blossom and spread faster. Communities also benefit from being able to exchange ideas on topical issues and on how to address new challenges as they arise. This all points to the need for an instrument that facilitates community meetings.

Open Science NL defines 'meeting' as national and international meetings, workshops, symposia, hackathons/doathons and conferences organised for and by parties in the field (see Chapter 7). The purpose of a meeting is training, fostering the exchange of experiences, knowledge and ideas and promoting collaborations so that open science practices can be developed and spread faster. If necessary, a meeting may include a number of successive moments (e.g. several meetings for writing a position paper or guide to open science practices).

3 Conditions for applicants

This chapter contains the conditions that are applicable to your grant application. Firstly it describes who can apply for funding (Section 3.1) and what you can request funding for (Section 3.2). Subsequently, you will find the conditions for preparing and submitting the application (Sections 3.3 and 3.4) and the specific funding conditions (Section 3.5).

3.1 Who can apply

Full, associate and assistant professors, academic staff, PhD candidates, and research support staff, such as community managers, research software engineers, data stewards, programme coordinators and comparable positions may submit an application if they have a position at one of the following organisations:

- universities and universities of applied sciences (UAS) as referred to in Article 1.8 paragraph 1 of the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act and universities listed in the [Policy Rules for Universities located in the Kingdom of the Netherlands](#);
- university medical centres by which is meant academic hospitals as referred to in Article 1.13 paragraph 1 of the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act;
- institutes affiliated to the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) or NWO;
- Netherlands Cancer Institute;
- the Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics in Nijmegen;
- Naturalis Biodiversity Center;
- Advanced Research Centre for NanoLithography (ARCNL);
- Princess Máxima Center.

Persons with a zero-hour employment agreement may not submit a proposal.

Employees with a position at one of the following societal parties, established in the Netherlands, may act as co-applicant. In this Call for proposals, the following societal parties are allowed as co-applicant:

- museums;
- libraries;
- patient organisations;
- citizen collectives.

Additional condition:

- Each applicant may submit a maximum of one application per year.

[De minimis threshold for societal parties acting as co-applicant](#)

Societal parties acting as co-applicants may receive funding from Open Science NL provided that the de minimis threshold as stated in the De Minimis Regulation (EU Regulation no. 2023/2831 of the European Commission on 13 December 2023) is not exceeded. On the basis of the De Minimis Regulation, a societal party acting as a co-applicant may receive € 300,000 in state aid in total during a period of three years.

By submitting a de minimis statement, the societal party declares that if the party receives the funding from Open Science NL they will not exceed the de minimis threshold. If the societal party concludes that the de minimis threshold is exceeded through the funding of Open Science NL, they cannot apply for funding from Open Science NL. The main applicant needs to consider this in composing the project budget, and consequently needs to check per societal party that the de minimis threshold is not exceeded through this funding. All involved societal parties need to submit a de minimis statement individually as part of the application.

3.1.1 Main and co-applicants

The main applicant submits the proposal via the NWO web application ISAAC. During the assessment process, NWO will communicate with the main applicant.

After a proposal has been awarded funding, the main applicant will become the project leader and point of contact for NWO. The knowledge institution of the main applicant is the main beneficiary and will become the official secretary.

Co-applicants have an active role in realising the project. The (sub)project leaders and beneficiary/beneficiaries are jointly responsible for realising the entire project.

3.2 What can be applied for

Calculation of the total requested budget consists of two components. Firstly, you can apply for € 100 per participant per day, with a total maximum of € 15,000. You can subsequently divide the budget over the eligible budget modules stated below to your own understanding.

Secondly, you may request a maximum of € 2,000 for a maximum of five foreign speakers, living outside of the Netherlands, for travel and accommodation costs. This reimbursement is on top of the reimbursement per participant, but should remain below the € 15,000 total maximum.

Eligible participants include (a) scientific personnel (b) supporting staff (c) relevant staff from the corporate domain and (d) staff from relevant public organisations. Staff from these eligible categories may work both in and outside of the Netherlands.

This Call for proposals is not aimed at internal meetings within an institution. Therefore, a minimum of 1/3 of the total participants should be external participants.

Eligible and ineligible costs

The grant is solely intended to facilitate the meeting. This means that Open Science NL only contributes to costs for:

- the design and use of a digital platform on which the meeting takes place (including recording costs);
- renting facilities (room, studio, technical resources, computer, video projector);
- printing costs for promotional materials (flyers, posters);
- accommodation costs for participants (coffee, tea, lunch, dinner, reception, overnight stay);
- travel and accommodation costs for speakers;
- costs for making the meeting physically and/or digitally accessible for participants with disabilities (including costs for travel assistance and costs for digital support).

Ineligible for funding are:

- costs for dinner and drinks only that are not preceded by a substantive programme;
- symposium volumes (book of abstracts);
- gifts;
- hiring of a congress bureau or conference office;
- prizes.

Non-admissible events

You cannot submit an application for:

- closed meetings;
- Olympiads;
- existing courses and training programmes;
- digital meetings;
- meetings honouring researchers, such as farewell and other symposiums, inaugural lectures, thesis defence ceremonies and similar personal gatherings or other celebratory occasions;
- activities organised by study societies and student associations;
- meetings already funded by Open Science NL or NWO through other funding instruments, including meetings organised at the Lorentz Center.

Series and sub-meetings

You cannot apply for a series of meetings. You and your co-organisers may apply for funding per individual event in a series. The programme and participants should be clear before submitting an application. Without this information, Open Science NL cannot check if the application is admissible for funding according to the conditions stated in this Call.

You can apply for an open science meeting which is part of an overarching meeting with a broader substantive objective. However, only the part that has open science (see Annex in Chapter 7) as its subject will be funded.

3.3 Preparing an application

The steps involved in writing your application are:

- download the application form from the NWO web application ISAAC or from the NWO web page (on the grant page of the funding instrument concerned);
- complete the application form;
- save the application form in ISAAC as a PDF file and upload it with any compulsory annexes;
- fill in the requested information online in ISAAC.

Optional annex:

- de minimis statement (mandatory for societal parties acting as co-applicants).

The application and optional de minimis statement must be drawn up in accordance with the template provided by Open Science NL. Annexes must be uploaded in ISAAC separately from the application.

You must write your application in Dutch or English.

Annexes other than the optional annex stated above are not allowed.

An application can only be submitted via the web application ISAAC. Applications that are not submitted via ISAAC will not be taken into consideration.

As the main applicant, you are required to submit the application via your own personal ISAAC account.

It is important to start with your application in ISAAC on time:

- if you do not yet have an ISAAC account, then you should create this on time to prevent any possible registration problems;
- any new research organisations must also be added to ISAAC by NWO;
- you also need to submit other details online.

Applications submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration by Open Science NL.

For technical questions, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk, see contact (Chapter 6).

Applicants are expected to have informed the research organisation where they work about submitting the application and that the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this Call for proposals.

3.3.1 Advice about substantive suitability

For this Call for proposals your application has to fit within the themes of open science (see Chapter 7).

Please decide well in advance if your application fits substantively. If you have doubts concerning the substantive fit of your application, you should contact the contact person from the programme well before the deadline. They can advise you about the substantive fit in this Call for proposals. Please note that the final choice is yours. For contact details, please see section 6.1.1.

3.4 Conditions for submission

3.4.1 Formal conditions for submission

Open Science NL will assess your application against all the conditions set out in this Call for proposals, including the conditions listed below. Your application will only be admitted to the assessment procedure if it meets these conditions. After submitting your application, Open Science NL requests you to be available to implement any possible administrative corrections so that you can (still) meet the conditions for submission.

These conditions are:

- the meeting takes place in the Kingdom of the Netherlands;
- the main applicant and optional co-applicant(s) meet the conditions stated in Section 3.1;
- the application complies with the DORA guidelines as described in Section 4.1;
- the application is submitted via the main applicant's ISAAC account;
- the application is received before the deadline;
- the application is written in Dutch or English;
- the application is received within the submission period; i.e. a minimum of six weeks and a maximum of twelve months before the meeting takes place;
- the application budget is drawn up in accordance with the conditions for this Call for proposals.

All (mandatory) annexes have been submitted, after request for addition or adjustment of information, in accordance with the instructions and conditions stated in the Call for proposals and application form.

3.5 Conditions on granting

The [NWO Grant Rules 2024](#) and the [Agreement on the Payment of Costs for Scientific Research](#) are applicable to all applications.

The applicant should send the final programme to Open Science NL at most one week before the event. After receiving the grant award decision, the applicant should also communicate about the support of Open Science NL externally, especially to the participants of the event. This may be achieved through adding the Open Science NL logo (see www.openscience.nl/en/corporate-identity) to the website, the welcome slide in a presentation, the programme flyer/book or other promotion materials.

Open Science NL maintains a close professional relationship with the open science communities. When possible and desirable, Open Science NL may cooperate in organisation or execution of the event.

3.5.1 Compliance with the National Knowledge Security Guidelines

World-class science can benefit from international cooperation. The National Knowledge Security Guidelines (hereafter: the Guidelines) helps knowledge institutions to ensure that international cooperation can take place securely. Knowledge security concerns the undesirable transfer of sensitive knowledge and technology that compromises national security; the covert influence of state actors on education and research, which jeopardises academic freedom and social safety; and ethical issues that may arise in cooperation with countries that do not respect fundamental rights.

Applicants are responsible for ensuring that their project complies and will continue to comply with the Guidelines. By submitting an application, the applicant commits to the recommendations stipulated in these Guidelines. In the event of a suspected breach of the Guidelines in an application submitted to NWO for project funding, or in a project funded by NWO, NWO may ask the applicant to provide a risk assessment demonstrating that the recommendations in the Guidelines have been taken into consideration. If the applicant fails to comply with NWO's request, or if the risk assessment is in apparent breach of the Guidelines, this may affect NWO's grant award or decision-making process. NWO may also include further conditions in the award letter if appropriate.

The National Knowledge Security Guidelines can be found on the central government website at: [Home | National Contact Point for Knowledge Security \(loketkennisveiligheid.nl\)](#).

3.5.2 Scientific integrity

In accordance with the NWO Grant Rules 2024, the project that NWO funds must be carried out in accordance with the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018). By submitting the proposal, the applicant commits to this code. In the case of a (possible) violation of these standards during a project funded by NWO, the applicant should immediately inform NWO of this and should submit all relevant documents to NWO. More information about the code of conduct and the policy regarding research integrity can be found on the website: [Scientific integrity | NWO](#).

3.5.3 Ethical statement or licence

The applicant is responsible for determining whether an ethical statement or licence is needed for the realisation of the proposed project. The applicant should ensure that this is obtained from the relevant institution or ethics committee on time. The absence or presence of an ethical statement or licence at the time of the application process has no effect on the assessment of the application. If the project is awarded funding, then the grant is issued under the condition that the necessary ethical statement or licence is obtained before the latest start date for the project. The project cannot start until NWO has received a copy of the ethical statement or licence.

3.5.4 Nagoya Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol ensures an honest and reasonable distribution of benefits emerging from the use of genetic resources (Access and Benefit Sharing; ABS). Researchers who make use of genetic sources from the Netherlands or abroad for their research should familiarise themselves with the Nagoya Protocol ([Home - ABS Focal Point](#)). NWO assumes that researchers will take all necessary actions with respect to the Nagoya Protocol.

4 Assessment procedure

This chapter first describes the assessment according to the DORA principles (Section 4.1) and the course of the assessment procedure (Section 4.2). Second, it states the criteria that the assessment committee will use to assess your application (Section 4.3).

The NWO Code for Dealing with Personal Interests applies to all persons and NWO employees involved in the assessment and/or decision-making process ([Code for Dealing with Personal Interests | NWO](#)).

NWO strives to achieve an inclusive culture where there is no place for conscious or unconscious barriers due to cultural, ethnic or religious background, gender, sexual orientation, health or age ([Diversity and inclusion | NWO](#)). NWO encourages those involved in the assessment to be actively aware of implicit associations and to try to minimise these. NWO will provide them with information about concrete ways of improving the assessment of an application.

4.1 The San Francisco Declaration (DORA)

NWO is a signatory to the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). DORA is a worldwide initiative that aims to improve the way research and researchers are assessed. DORA contains recommendations for research funders, research institutions, scientific journals and other parties.

DORA aims to reduce the uncritical use of bibliometric indicators and obviate unconscious bias in the assessment of research and researchers. DORA's overarching philosophy is that research should be evaluated on its own merits rather than on the basis of surrogate measures, such as the journal in which the research is published.

When assessing the scientific track record of applicants, NWO makes use of a broad definition of scientific output.

For more information on how NWO is implementing the principles of DORA, see [DORA | NWO](#).

4.2 Procedure

The application procedure consists of the following steps:

- submission of the proposal;
- admissibility of the proposal;
- decision-making.

4.2.1 Submission of a proposal

For the submission of the proposal, a standard form is available on the funding page of this Call for proposals on the Open Science NL website. When you write your proposal, you must adhere to the questions stated on this form and the procedure given in the explanatory notes. You must also adhere to the conditions for the maximum number of words and pages.

Your complete application form must have been received before the deadline via ISAAC (see Section 1.3). After this deadline, you can no longer submit a proposal. After submitting the proposal, the main applicant will receive a confirmation of receipt.

4.2.2 Admissibility of the proposal

As soon as possible after you have submitted your proposal, you will hear from Open Science NL whether or not your proposal will be taken into consideration. Open Science NL will determine this based on several administrative-technical criteria (see the formal conditions for submission, Section 3.4). Open Science NL can only take your proposal into consideration if it meets these conditions.

Please bear in mind that within two weeks after the submission deadline, Open Science NL may approach you with any possible administrative corrections that need to be made so that your proposal can (still) meet the conditions for submission. You will be given one opportunity to make the corrections, and you will be given five working days to do this.

4.2.3 Decision-making

Open Science NL does not seek external advice for the assessment of the proposals in this Call. The Open Science NL Office assesses the application and related documents. Finally, the Steering Board of Open Science NL will assess the procedure followed and the advice of the Office. Subsequently it determines the final qualifications and makes a decision on awarding or rejecting the proposals.

4.2.4 Timetable

Open Science NL will consider the applications in the order in which they are received. Every six weeks, the Open Science NL Steering Board takes decisions on the applications for meetings that have been submitted up to that date. A decision will be announced to the applicant within six weeks.

4.3 Criteria

4.3.1 Substantive assessment criteria

The applications submitted within this Call for proposals will be substantially assessed on the basis of the following criteria:

1. Fit of the meeting within the field of open science (see chapter 7)
2. Fit of the meeting within the goal of the Call for proposals (see chapter 2).

The proposal must receive an overall qualification of at least 'good' to be eligible for funding.

5 Obligations for grant recipients

This chapter details the various obligations that - in addition to the conditions stated in Section 3.5 - apply after funds have been awarded.

5.1 Additional terms and conditions

5.1.1 Open Access

NWO is committed to making the results of scientific research funded by NWO freely accessible via the internet (Open Access). NWO thereby fulfils the Dutch government's policy to make all publicly funded research open access. Scientific publications of research funded based on allocations resulting from this Call for Proposals should therefore be available in Open Access according to the Open Access Policy. For a further explanation of NWO's Open Access policy see: [Open Science | NWO](#). Other products resulting from projects funded through this Call for proposals should also be shared as openly as possible under an open licence. Examples include presentations, reports, working papers, posters, etc. It is advised to share these outputs via a trusted repository, such as registered on [OpenDOAR¹](#).

¹ <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/>

6 Contact and other information

6.1 Contact

6.1.1 Specific questions

For specific questions about this Call for proposals, please contact:

Mirjam Teunissen
Tel no. +31(0) 70 349 42 43
opensciencemeetings@nwo.nl

6.1.2 Technical questions about the web application ISAAC

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Please read the manual first before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk can be contacted from Monday to Friday between 10:00 and 17:00 hours on +31 (0)70 34 40 600. However, you can also submit your question by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will then receive an answer within two working days.

6.2 Other information

The whole text of this Call for proposals has been published in both Dutch and English. The Dutch version is deemed authentic. For legal interpretation the text of the Dutch version will be decisive.

Open Science NL processes data from applicants received in the context of this Call for proposals in accordance with the NWO Privacy Statement, [Privacy Statement | NWO](#).

Open Science NL might approach applicants for an evaluation of the procedure and/or research programme.

7 Annexes

7.1 Definition of Open Science

Applications for this Call for proposals should fit within the field of open science. For this Call for proposals, the following definition of open science is used, in accordance with the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#):

“Open science is an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices:

- to make scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone;*
- to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society;*
- and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.*

Open science comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.

Open Science is focused on all kinds of research outcomes: open scientific publications, open research data, open metadata, open educational resources, open source software and source code, and open hardware”.

Publication: January 2025

Dutch Research Council

Visiting address:

Location The Hague

Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië

2593 CE The Hague

Netherlands

Location Utrecht

Winthontlaan 2

3526 KV Utrecht

Cover image: credits Shutterstock

Dutch Research Council | [NWO](#)

[Open Science NL](#)

